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A GEOGRAPHICAL ANYLISIS OF FRUIT CROP COMBINATION IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT:

India is the third largest producer of fruits. The contribution of horticulture is estimated to be around 25%. The area under fruits is estimated to be 3.23 million hectares. The concept of crop combination is scientific device to study. The study of crop combination regions constitutes an important aspect of Agricultural Geography, as it provides a good basis for agriculture. Fruit accounts for about 10% of gross value in total Indian agricultural produce & 13% of export earnings. There are six fruit growing regions in Maharashtra. The development of fruit farming on commercial lines has taken place during the last two decades in the study area. In the period under investigation positive changes with respect to area and fruit varieties. This district grows fruits such as Grape, Pomegranate, Ber, Mango, Guava Lime, Chikku, Banana etc in the region.

Key Words: Export earning, Leading device, combination, existing, dry farming,

INTRODUCTION:

Fruit farming is one time investment and long time earning of process. Fruit crops play a distinctive role in the Indian economy by improving the income of the rural people. Cultivation of fruit crops plays a vital role in the prosperity of the nation and is directly linked with the health and happiness of the Indian people. Fruit crop combination is an important aspect.

Fruit farming means cultivation of fruit crops in large area in open fields on a commercial scale. Fruit farming is the science and arts of growing fruit plants and region is the specific field where variety of fruits are grown. In the recent years the planners and policy makers in the developing economies are more interested in the contribution of fruit farming . India accounts for about 10 percent of the production of fruits in the world.

Fruit farming is also very important because the well maintained established orchards give better returns than traditional crops. Horticulture contributes over 24.5 percent agriculture GDP.

SELECTION OF THE STUDY REGION:

The region under study i.e. Solapur district lies to the southern part of Maharashtra state on the border of Maharashtra and Karnataka State. The district of Solapur lies between 17⁰5' to 18⁰32' north latitudes and 74⁰42' to 76⁰15' east longitudes. It is surrounded by Ahmadnagar district to the north, Osmanabad district to the north-east, Karnataka state to the south-east, Sangli district to the south-west, Satara district to the west and Pune district to the north-west.

Solapur district has an area of 14878 sq. km. and population 43,15,527 persons as per 2011 census.

The region under investigation has been influenced by several considerations.

1. Solapur district comprising eleven tahsils of Maharashtra state has a significant location on Maharashtra plateau. Out of the total geographical area 3.34 percent area is occupied by hilly region and 16.66 percent is occupied by lowland region and remaining 80 percent region is plateau region which is useful for fruit crops. The Bhima and Nira are the major rivers of the region.

2. Climatically entire region falls in the rain shadow area.

3. The study region has irrigation facilities through wells, tube wells and canals

4. Soils of the region are mainly derived from trap rocks.

5. Out of the total working population nearly 30 percent working population is engaged in primary economic activities.

6. The study region has a fairly good system of road and rail network.

7. Farmers of this region have given much response to "Phalodyan Vikas Yojana" (1990-91) and innovations in water supply systems, particularly drip irrigation system.

Fig No.1

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To assess the fruit crop combination in the study region.
2. To evaluate the causes of crop concentration in the study region.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY:

Data has been collected through primary and secondary sources. Secondary data has been obtained from socio-economic reviews of the district, district census handbooks, gazetteers. The data has been classified, tabulated and analyzed by using various statistical techniques and presented by using various cartographic methods.

In the present work Solapur District is selected as a study region in general and each tahsil of the district as a component areal unit. Period of investigation is of fifteen years (2010-11). The varieties of major fruit crop of the region considered for micro level analysis.

Sum of the methods used in the analysis of the present study are given below.

In the present study Weaver's method is used for fruit crop combination. The procedure of this technique is explained as follows-

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum d^2}{n}}$$

However, as Weaver pointed out, the relative, not absolute value being significant, square roots were extracted, so the actual formula used was as follows:-

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\sum d^2}{n}$$

Where,

d = the difference between the crop percentage in a given areal unit and the percentage in the theoretical percentage.

n = the number of crops in a given combination.

4.11 FRUIT CROP COMBINATION:

Any study of crops on the regional scale must take into consideration the combinational analysis and the relative position of the crops. The concept of crop combination is a scientific device to study the existing spatial relationship of crops in association with each other in Agriculture Geography and land utilization.

The study of crop combination regions constitutes an important aspect of Agriculture Geography, as it provides a good basis for agriculture regionalization. Crops are generally grown in combination and it is rarely that a particular crop occupies a position in total isolation from other crops in a given aerial unit at a given point of time. In recent years, the concept of crop combination has engaged the attention of geographers and agriculture land-use planners.

So crop combination regions are delineated here on the basis of methods advocated by Weaver J.C. (1954). The most important and popular approach is presented by J C Weaver for delineating the complex structure of agricultural regions of middle-west in the USA in 1954. In this study, he has taken into account the percentage of crop area to total cropped area and has calculated the deviation of real percentage for all the possible combinations in the component areal units against a theoretical standard.

The theoretical curve for standard measurement was employed as follows:

Monoculture = 100 % of the total harvested crop land in one crop

2 crop combination = 50 % in each of two crops

3 crop combination = 33.3 % in each of three crops

4 crop combination = 25 % in each of four crops

5 crop combination = 20 % in each of five crops

10 crop combination = 10 % in each of ten crops

For the determination of the minimum deviation the standard deviation method was used by using above formula.

As a result of the statistical processing by Weaver's deviation method, 6 fruit crops combination regions are identified in Solapur District from the main 10 fruit crops.

Crop Combination, according to J.C.Weaver's Method:

The Weaver's method has been admirably accepted for the delineation of crop combination regions as its application result is suitable for combination. The method, however, gives the most unwieldy combination for the units of high crop specification.

As a result of the application of the Weaver's method, six fruit crop combination regions emerge out in Solapur district. The talukas falling into different combinations as per reference year 2010-11 are given in table No.1

Table No. 1 Fruit Crop Variance according to Weaver's Method 2010-11

Crop comb	Karm	Mad	Bars	Nort h Sola	Moh ol	Pan dha	Mal shir	San gola	Man g	Sout h Sola p	Akk al
Mono	5184	3969	5329	2704	4225	1936	5184	1296	2116	4096	4900
2	690	171	685	452	377	562	634	578	468	642	420
3	219	197	187	357	138	411	202	630	427	190	87
4	123		90	283	120	398	95		390	91	102
5	83		66	246	121	376	76		395	106	
6	73		54	236		368	69				

Source: - Compiled by Researcher

Table No.2 Crop Combination according to Weaver's Method 2010-11

Fruit Crop Combination	No of talukas	Name of talukas	Name of Fruit Crops
Mono	-	-	-
2	2	Madha Sangola	Ber, pomegranate pomegranate, Ber
3	1	Akkalkot	Ber, mango, lime
4	3	Mohol Mangalwedha South Solapur	Pomegranate, ber, lime, grape Pomegranate, ber, mango, lime Grape, mango, ber, lime
5	-	-	-
6	5	Karmala Barshi North Solapur Pandharpur Malshiras	Mango, ber, lime, grape, coconut, pomeg. Guava Ber, grape, mango, lime, sweet lime, pomeg. Grape, ber, mango, lime, pomeg., chinch Pomeg., grape, ber, mango, lime, chiku Pomeg., ber, grape, mango, lime, chiku

Source: - Compiled by researcher

Fig No. 2

1. Two -crop Combination

Table no.1 and Fig No.1 shows that the pattern of monoculture crop combination are absent in the reference years 2010-11. Two tehasils have the two-fruit crop covering considerable cultivated area of the region in the reference year 2010-11. Scanty rainfall, receptivity of black soil and lack of irrigation facilities have also led to the cultivation of pomegranate and ber which are generally drought resistant crop in Sangola and Madha tehasils of Solapur district.

However, the quality of pomegranate is very high in Sangola tehasil due to the fact that pomegranate is popular all over the world. At present pomegranate farmers face the problem of *telya* disease and drought condition. After the development of irrigation facilities, the area enjoyed by ber in Madha tehasil has been replaced by the cash crops like sugarcane and cotton.

2. Three-crop Combination: - This crop combination is observed only in Akkalkot tehasil. In this tehasil ber, mango and lime fruit crops are cultivated, but it is cultivated by traditional ways, so, per hectare benefit is low compared to the other tehasils.

3. Four-crop Combination: -

Four-crop combination is observed to have been implemented in three talukas (Mohol, Mangalwedha and South Solapur) in the year 2010-11. In these tehasils pomegranate, ber, mango, lime are common fruit crops which are largely cultivated. Grape is scientifically cultivated in South Solapur, especially in Nannaj village.

3. Six-crop Combination: -

This crop combination is found in five tahsils of the district in the reference year 2010-11, wherein mango, ber, lime, grape, coconut, pomegranate guava are seen to have cultivated. These five tehasils are Karmala, Malshiras, Barshi, Pandharpur and South Solapur. This may be due to the recent increase in irrigation facilities and improved techniques of dry farming.

CONCLUDING REMARKS:

Crop combination is an important aspect in Agricultural Geography, which is helpful to good agricultural regionalization. In this study area fruit crops area generally grown with combination. In this regard maximum six fruit combination is observed in the study region. Majority of six occupies the more than six fruit crop combination because farmers of the region are innovative and they cultivate commercial crops. Akkalkot tahsil is only one tahsil which suffering lack of irrigation hence there observed only three fruit crops mango, ber and lime which required very low water.

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